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After the independence of Uzbekistan, as in all spheres of life, reforms have been carried out in the education system, the introduction of modern information technologies in the educational process, the solution of computerization of education. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov's Decree of May 30, 2002 "On further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT)", Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 6, 2002 "On measures for further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies" Resolution, attached to the Resolution "Computerization and Information - development of communication technologies for 2002-2010 The State Program was adopted. These programs

ANALYSIS OF NEURAL NETWORK TRAINING TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the study of neural networks and their types. Areas of application of neural networks, applications cover a wide range of areas

information in higher educational institutions of the Republic new methods and tools for applying technology in the educational process organization, distance learning and Achieving computerized conferences, electronic creating textbooks and applying them in the educational process activities, prestigious projects on education reform, scientific research is underway.

Areas of application of neural networks, applications are diverse areas include: image perception, noisy information processing, image filling, associative search, classification, optimization, forecasting, diagnosis, signal processing, abstraction, process management and control, data segmentation, information compression chipping, complex reflection, complex processes modeling, machine vision

(electronic eye), speech comprehension and others.

The essence of the use of neural networks is in the economic sphere that is, this new method uses the previous traditional method that is, it does not exclude the methods being used does not recreate the bike, but these neuron nets are above has new capabilities designed to address the issues raised is a calculation tool. The future of neuronal species is very clear, today the knowledge in this area, activity in the field of computer technology showing scientific experts, as well as neighboring смежны many engineers and scientists working in the fields are about this have very clear assumptions.

Neural networks are such interconnected elements complexes, between which interrelationships must be ensured. Such elements are mainly called neurons or nodes and these in turn are simple processors. Their computing options are usually activation (activation) rules and login signals are limited by a combined rule, resulting in output signals on the input signal rods computing options are available. The output signal of the element is dimensional transmission to other elements via (coefficient) bonds possible. Each of the senders is divided into weights or weightshas Depending on the value of the weight coefficients are transmitted the signal is amplified or reduced.

There are many, many different types of neural networks, however all nets are generalized in a number of respects have the characteristics, abstract them as follows at the present time can be described in appearance:

- a set of simple processors;

- structure of connections;
- rules of network signal distribution;
- rules for combining input signals;
- rules for calculating the activity signal;
- corrective links, training rules.

The ability to learn neural networks is their traditional one is one of the important advantages over algorithms. Technically studies the coefficients of connection (weight) between neurons is to find. Neural network input and output in the learning process to determine the complex relationship between, as well as different able to make generalizations. Successful learning as a result, the neural network has the ability to switch to operating modes directly, as well as based on “noisy”, incomplete or partially distorted data. The neural network is associated with analog and discrete error moments functions are considered as secondary optimization functions. Iterative search in the process of building integrated systems components of the neural network needed to form is obtained by calculating the functional parameters. From this In addition, the main task is the secondary optimization function is done by estimating the gradient vector. Neural networks can be implemented in two ways:

1. Programmatic model of artificial neural networks;
2. Hardware implementation of artificial neural networks.

The basic hardware artificial neural networks product is mostly artificial created on the basis of neurobiological systems (neurobis). At the moment adaptive solutions (ssha) and hitachi from

the neurons being created (Japanese) firms can be distinguished. Adaptive solutions The firm's neurobiology is running very fast, its announcement The processing speed is 1.2 billion. Connection/sec. (neural network 64 neuron and 262144 synapses). A neurobiologist from Hitachi up to 576 neurons in the artificial neural network created on the basis of possible. Many of these neurobes specialize in being considered a new generation can form the basis of processor neurocomputers.

Most modern neurocomputers are personal computers or describes a workstation whose composition is an additional neuroplate enters. Such computers include, for example, fmr series computers from Fujitsu. The capabilities of neurocomputers based on this principle are numerous in practice able to solve problems by neuromathematic methods. However, specialized neurocomputers are of great interest, they directly implement the principles of neural networks. Representatives of such systems belong to the brand family of the firm Trw computers (the first perceptron created by Rosenblatt implementation, called Mark I).

Trw's Mark III model represents a workstation, it belongs to the family of mathematical coprocessors Motorola 68000 There are up to 15 processors. The architecture of the system is up to 65,000 supports virtual processor elements that are, 1 has more than a million adjustable links, 450,000 intervals link / s. Able to process up to. The Mark IV is a single-processor with a conveyor architecture supercomputer. It supports up to 236,000 virtual processor elements supports up to 5 million intermediate connections / s. Processing capable of. Another model is the

Netsim computer, developed by Texas Instruments on the basis of developments from the University of Cambridge. Its topology is in the form of a three-dimensional grid with standard computing nodes created on the basis of 80188 processors. The Netsim computer is used to model such neural networks as Hopfield-cochone and reverse scattering neural networks. His job capacity up to 450 million intermediate link / s. Recyclability has In the implementation of all methods of training neural networks we face different problems. The neural network within a specified time there is no guarantee that he will learn to read. Artificial neural network training the algorithm can fall to the "local minimum" and the result is good we may not be able to find a solution.

A very big problem is the strength of the neural networks depending on. Like humans, the structure of the brain imitates them, the net stores in the memory of something unpredictable. Artificial neuron the only way to know the exact value of the outgoing quantity in the network available, even if it is all combinations of input signals should be considered. Such a thorough inspection is practically done non-existent situation and the use of statistical methods for this necessary.

The conclusion is in place

Summarizing the experience of pedagogical science, scientific research of artificial systems, neural networks, theory of teaching- the more methodological apparatus, the more it can enrich a lot. Furthermore except for artificial neural networks training procedures the logic of the psychological and pedagogical aspects of the student in the formation review of

issues of detailing on the basis of principles, improvement is necessary. New computerized, neurotechnology-based information educational process as a result of the use of technology individualize, Informatics science (also in other sciences) in mastering, new motivations appear in students, the pupil-teacher evaluation of knowledge plays a strong role in the feedback system objectivity increases, statistical data collection is minimized, some aspects of mastering knowledge in students (good, low) manifests itself clearly, changing the structure of training in the teacher possibility (corresponding to the initial preparatory level of students it turns out, the possibility of differentiation of the educational process creates, increases the level of mastering the subject, science, increase interest in it.

Modern neuro-learning process computerized the use of technology makes the teacher more technical and technological supports, communicate live

with students saving is much the only time, as a result, pupils with possible communication in a human and individual way, close to each other in a relationship, it will be in the form of a master-shogird. The subject training model considered on the basis of neurotarmac technology can be used to address the following issues:

- Teacher and controlling computerised flexibility to build systems;
- More in-depth study and theory of artificial neural networks to develop;

Higher education questions of artificial neural network technology wide introduction to the activity, in particular, the knowledge gained by students degree in the areas of concrete subject areas, in the areas of Education evaluation, which in turn correspond to the methods of training there will be a basis for making corrections.

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